

Research Paper

Experimental analysis of a reversible high-temperature heat pump/ORC test rig for geothermal CHP applications

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ABSTRACT

Reversible high-temperature heat pumps (HTHP) are a promising technology for the application in geothermal combined heat and power (CHP) plants. The HTHP operation enables clean peak load coverage of an attached district heating network (DHN) during the winter, replacing fossil boilers, while reversible operation as an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) generates electricity from otherwise unused geothermal heat during the summer. This work presents the experimental characterisation of a novel fully reversible HTHP/ORC test rig, designed for the application in geothermal CHP plants. The test rig is supplied by a 200 kW hot water heating circuit as a heat source and uses a fully reversible 20 kW twin-screw machine as compressor and expander. A closed-loop intermediate cooling circuit allows simulating a DHN with varying temperature levels and mass flows during HTHP operation. The HTHP is capable of thermal loads up to 110 kW at heat sink outlet temperatures of up to 120 °C, making it well suited for geothermal CHP applications. For investigated temperature lifts between 25 K and 57 K, COPs between 6.4 and 3.0 are observed. During ORC operation, net electric thermal efficiencies of 5-6% and maximum net electric system efficiencies of 2.5% are achieved for various heat source mass flow rates and temperatures between 110 °C and 130 °C. The oil separator is identified as a major limitation in both operational modes and should be replaced by a larger version to enhance efficiency and plant capacity. Furthermore, the oil delivery to the compressor needs to be optimised during HTHP operation in further studies.

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation and state-of-the-art

Within the last years, reversible high-temperature heat pump (rHTHP) systems have gained significant attention as a promising solution for the flexible and economical supply of heat and electricity. These reversible systems are generally capable of operating either as a high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) or as an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC), making them especially suitable for combined heat and power (CHP) plants. Since there is no clear definition of an rHTHP in literature with respect to plant layout and functionality, the term “reversible heat pump” is sometimes also used for regular heat pumps capable of heating and cooling. However, in this work the term solely refers to plants capable of ORC and HTHP operation, following the wording in the ORC and HTHP community. While an ORC uses low-temperature

heat from various sources (e.g. geothermal, waste heat or solar) to generate electricity [1], an HTHP upgrades otherwise unused heat like ambient or low-temperature waste heat to a useful temperature level while consuming electricity [2].

Multiple applications for rHTHP systems have been proposed. One of the first was their use for flexible heat and electricity generation in residential applications, more specifically in a Net-Zero-Energy-Building, proposed by Dumont et al. [3]. In their work, the authors experimentally determined an ORC cycle efficiency of 4.2% (at 3.7 kW power output) and a heat pump COP of 3.1, respectively. They moreover highlight the importance of component selection and associated problems (i.e. with high pressure losses) for reversible systems [3]. Based on that concept, Quoilin et al. confirmed the technology's ability to produce significant amounts of electricity (next to its primary task of space heating) by means of annual simulations [4]. After optimising

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some constructional and operational system parameters, the authors report a yearly electricity production of 3500 kWh by the ORC. In a simulative study, Kosmadakis & Panagiotis show the potential for increased profits of an rHTHP compared to mono-functional plants in an industrial context despite their higher initial cost. Their results indicate decreasing economic viability of reversible configurations (compared to heat delivery by a gas boiler) with increasing heat pump capacity [5]. Steinmann et al. (2019) present various application scenarios for rHTHPs serving as a sector-coupling technology to decarbonise the heat and electricity supply [6]. In a similar context, Urbanucci et al. highlight the ecological and economic advantages of an rHTHP compared to conventional (fossil) backup technologies for peak load times. In their study, carbon dioxide emissions were reduced by 11% while the annual cost of the considered micro-CHP trigeneration system dropped by 7% [7].

The recently most investigated application of rHTHPs is their use in pumped thermal electricity storages (PTES). Frate et al. introduce a thermally integrated PTES relying on a rHTHP and investigate the effect of different heat source temperatures and working fluids. In accordance with other studies, they recommend R1233zd(E) as the most promising working fluid achieving a maximum roundtrip efficiency of 1.3 with thermal integration of a heat source at 110 °C [8]. Staub et al. consider the effect of different process topologies on the roundtrip efficiency of PTES systems. Their results indicate roundtrip efficiencies of around 0.5 when the heat source temperature is limited to 80 °C and realistic component constraints are considered [9]. Looking at a similar topic as the previously mentioned authors, Ma et al. conduct a thermo-economic analysis and optimisation for reversible HTHP/ORC systems in a PTES, identifying R1233zd(E) as the best-suited working fluid in concordance with other authors [10]. Their study suggests an optimum storage temperature glide between 99 °C and 126 °C, achieving a power-to-power efficiency of 28.16%. While Dumont et al. first validated the reversible use of scroll machines as compressors and expanders, this was also achieved by Steger et al. for twin-screw machines in a PTES test rig yielding efficiencies of 1–4% in ORC mode and COPs of 4–6 in heat pump mode [3,11]. On the same test rig, Weitzer et al. later yielded a maximum efficiency of 4.4% in ORC mode and a maximum COP of 9.5 in HTHP mode by optimising the operational strategy and fluid charge [12]. The test rig was further investigated based on its performance as a thermally integrated Carnot battery, yielding a power-to-power efficiency of 41.8% [13]. In a recent study, the same authors examined the operation of their rHTHP test rig using zeotropic fluid mixtures in order to optimise overall system efficiency [14]. Both experimental and simulation results demonstrate that zeotropic mixtures reduce exergy losses and enable notable efficiency improvements. The findings indicate an increase in efficiency from 3.31% to 4.46% in ORC mode and in COP from 5.16 to 7.09 in HTHP mode, with relative improvements of 23% and 11%, respectively.

Another recent work by Velanparambil Ravindran et al. experimentally evaluates a small-scale reversible HTHP for waste heat recovery applications. Their test-rig design is similar to the one presented in this work but uses a small reversible scroll compressor, making it less relevant for large-scale industrial applications [15]. The experimental set-up of Velanparambil Ravindran et al. is based on simulative pre-studies, which discuss important aspects related to system layout, component selection and the optimal working fluid [16]. The dual use of an rHTHP's core components (i.e. the compressor and heat exchangers) is a significant achievement for improving the economic viability of rHTHP plants. However, several authors point out that the efficiency of reversibly used compressors significantly decreases in at least one operational mode due to the different process conditions calling for optimisation in system design and machine integration [8,9,17]. In a recent simulative work, Guo et al. propose the design of an off-grid rHTHP combined with PV panels to meet the electricity and cooling needs of a Nigerian family farm [18]. By optimising system parameters and incorporating an ice storage and an electric heater, the design

achieves improved efficiency, reducing reliance on diesel generators and grid power, using R152a as working fluid.

A further promising application for rHTHPs is their use in geothermal combined heat and power plants, which was previously analysed by the authors [19,20]. Here, the primary task of the geothermal well is to supply heat to a district heating network (DHN). Excess heat during low heat demand times is used to generate electricity with the ORC. When the geothermal heat is insufficient for the DHN during peak load times, the plant operates in HTHP mode and takes load from a fossil peak load boiler while further cooling down the geothermal brine. The respective plant layout, including the main cycle components for ORC and HTHP, is depicted in Fig. 1. The results of a recent detailed techno-economic analysis of the proposed plant concept indicate that rHTHPs and HTHPs are most competitive for higher gas prices, and the rHTHP system is well suited to lower the investment risk, as it shows a high resilience towards fluctuating electricity prices [21]. The application of rHTHPs for geothermal district heating was later also investigated by Daniarta et al. [22], but their analysis merely provided a rather superficial investigation based on energy balances.

1.2. Motivation and contribution

As the previous section shows, experimental evaluations of rHTHPs are scarce. In particular, only two simulative studies investigate the suitability of rHTHPs for geothermal CHP applications, not answering any questions regarding technical feasibility and efficiency of an rHTHP for the operating conditions commonly found in geothermal CHP facilities. Hence, an rHTHP test rig for geothermal applications was recently built by the authors [20], which aims at validating the proposed plant concept for geothermal integration, flexibly supplying heat and power. Thus, this work extends the state of the art by presenting the first operation of a fully reversible HTHP test rig for geothermal application, using a reversible twin-screw compressor. While similar plant layouts have very recently been proposed for waste heat recovery [15], the plant concept provided in this work used a reversible twin-screw compressor instead of a small-scale scroll compressor. To the authors' best knowledge, this makes it the only available study to investigate a plant concept that allows for scaling the plant to an industrially relevant capacity, making the findings presented in this paper highly relevant for the technology's further advancement. The overarching goal is to determine the plant's flexibility and efficiency in both operational modes. For this purpose, extensive experiments are conducted in both operational modes. The HTHP is analysed with respect to its temperature lift dependent COP and its capability to supply a large range of thermal loads for various heat source and sink conditions. For the ORC, optimal operating parameters are determined for various heat source mass flows and temperatures. Finally, limitations of the current design are identified, and improvements for future studies are discussed. In summary, this work is the first study to provide an experimental investigation of a scalable rHTHP plant, judging its technical feasibility and efficiency for geothermal CHP applications. A major benefit of the proposed plant concept is the reversible use of all cycle components (whenever possible), yielding the highest potential for economic viability among all similar plant concepts proposed in the literature.

2. Material and methods

The following sections provide a description of the test rig used in this study. Moreover, the experimental procedures and the subsequent data processing and evaluation methods are described. Finally this chapter introduces the performance indicators used to evaluate the cycle and component efficiencies for both operating modes.

Fig. 1. Plant layout for a reversible HTHP integrated into a geothermal CHP plant with ORC (a) and HTHP (b) operation.

2.1. Test rig description

The test rig can be divided into three subsystems: the heating circuit, the cooling circuit and the combined working fluid and oil cycle. These subsystems are subsequently described. Fig. 2 shows a simplified P&ID of the constructed test rig to visualise the most important components and their connection. For the sake of clarity, not all components of the final test rig, such as various shut-off valves, sight glasses and other auxiliaries, are depicted. For a more detailed description of the design procedure and an in-depth description of all used components, the interested reader is referred to the authors' previous publication on this matter [20]. A thick line in Fig. 2 indicates vapour-only piping whereas liquid or two-phase piping is indicated by regular line thickness. For the sensory equipment labels, the abbreviations according to DIN EN 62424 were used. In this context the label's first letters F, P and T represent the process variables flow, pressure and temperature, respectively. The subsequent letters C, R and Z+ indicate the control of the respective process variable, its registration or a binary switching function with respect to an upper boundary value, respectively.

2.1.1. Heating circuit

As a heat source, the test rig uses a hot water circuit previously constructed for an ORC test rig at the Chair of Energy Systems of the Technical University of Munich. Here, only the most essential specifications of the heating circuit (HC) will be summarised, and the interested reader is referred to the detailed description by Eyerer et al. [23]. The heating circuit consists of a closed loop filled with water as the heating medium. The water is heated by a 200 kW electrical resistance heater whose power is adjusted via pulse width modulation, generating the required inlet temperature at the evaporator. The maximum temperature of the heating circuit is 140 °C, which aligns well with commonly observed wellhead temperatures of geothermal power production projects in southern Bavaria, Germany [24]. To keep it in a liquid state and hence mimic geothermal brine, the water inside the heating circuit is pressurised to a minimum relative pressure of 4.5 bar or higher, depending on the momentary temperature. The flow rate in the heating circuit is adjustable by a speed-controlled centrifugal pump and a bypass valve around the evaporator. While the pump can deliver up to 2.5 L/s of water to the evaporator, the actual obtainable flow rate in the heating circuit is strongly limited by the heating power of the resistance heater and hence depends on the temperature lift over the heater. The heating circuit sets a boundary condition for the working fluid cycle and can supply a wide variety of heat source flow rates and supply temperatures for both operational modes. Due to spatial limitations, the heating circuit is not fully depicted in Fig. 2 but only indicated as heat source in- and outflow at the evaporator together with the relevant sensors.

2.1.2. Cooling circuit

The intermediate cooling circuit (ICC) sets another boundary condition for the thermodynamic working fluid cycle, acting as the cold reservoir in both operational modes. It consists of a closed water loop, connecting the condenser in the working fluid circuit to the in-house primary cooling water line. The necessity for this ICC arises from the need to simulate a DHN during HTHP operation. The in-house cooling water supply temperature usually varies between 20 °C and 30 °C while the maximum allowed reflux temperature is 60 °C. Hence, an ICC is required to simulate elevated temperatures at the cold side of the condenser in HTHP mode. In HTHP mode, only HEX2 (c.f. Fig. 2) is in operation, while the 3-way ball valve (V-53) in the ICC is used to include HEX1 as well during ORC operation. For elevated temperatures in the ICC (e.g. a temperature lift of 90 °C to 110 °C), the heat transfer area between the primary cooling water and the ICC has to be limited in order to avoid cooling water reflux temperatures above 60 °C. Accordingly, only a small heat exchanger is used in HTHP mode, while a larger heat exchange area is desirable in ORC mode. A larger area leads to a smaller temperature approach between the primary cooling water and the ICC, effectively lowering the condensation temperature in the ORC and increasing its power output. The heat exchangers HEX1 (HEXONIC LB31-80H-5/4'') and HEX2 (SWEP B12Lx30) are brazed plate heat exchangers. A fixed speed centrifugal pump (Wilo Yonos Maxo plus 30/0,5-12) with a maximum flow rate of around 3 kg/s circulates the water in the ICC. A linear regulating valve (V-52, ESBE VLA121) at the pump head is used to control the flow rate in the ICC. A smaller version of the same valve type is used in the primary cooling water supply line to adjust the flow rate (V-54, ESBE VLE122). An inductive flow sensor (KROHNE OPTIFLUX 4050) is used to measure and control the water flow rate in the ICC. In addition, several PT100 class A temperature sensors and pressure transmitters (JUMO Midas) are integrated into the primary cooling water line and the ICC for monitoring and control purposes. The ICC can circulate water at various flow rates with temperatures between 30 °C and 120 °C. This enables changing condensation pressures in ORC mode and a multitude of simulated DHN states to test the HTHP's capabilities.

2.1.3. Working fluid and oil cycle

The combined working fluid and oil cycle is the core part of the test rig, enabling the operation of an ORC and a HTHP process in one shared apparatus. The eco-friendly HCFO refrigerant R1233zd(E) is selected as working fluid, since the literature consistently recommends it for rHTHP applications due to its favourable combination of safety properties (i.e. flammability and toxicity), low environmental impact and good thermodynamic performance that matches current standard refrigerants like R245fa [8,25,26]. The working fluid circuit uses manual 3-way ball valves (V-21, V-23, V-26 and V-30) to switch between ORC and HTHP operation. For both operation modes, the cycle starts

Fig. 2. Simplified P&ID of the constructed reversible ORC test rig with parts of the heating circuit. Main control loops for ORC (red) and HTHP (blue) operation.

with saturated working fluid, which is stored in a 30 L receiver vessel (A-Cold V8.AC.30.2). The receiver buffers fluctuations in the system's working fluid charge and allows for effective drainage of liquid from the condenser, increasing its effectiveness. Moreover, it acts as a vapour barrier towards the pump, avoiding dry running of the pump. A guided radar level sensor (KROHNE OPTIFLEX 1300C) monitors the liquid level in the receiver. In ORC mode, the working fluid is subcooled in a brazed plate heat exchanger (SWEP B8THx30) before entering the main pump (Verder Hydra-Cell G10 EKCEHFEMC) used to circulate the working fluid and increase its pressure. A 1.5 kW_{nom} induction motor (ecoDrives FCPA 100 L6/PHE) drives the pump at variable speed, allowing for simple pump speed and hence flow rate control. The degree of subcooling (to avoid pump cavitation) is controlled with a linear valve (V-51, ESBE VLA121) on the water side of the subcooler. In order to ensure sufficient subcooling in summer, the subcooler is connected to the tap water instead of the cooling water line. In HTHP mode, the pump is bypassed and the working fluid is directed to an electronic expansion valve (SIEMENS MVL661.20-2.5), which throttles the working fluid into the two-phase region. A Coriolis flow meter (KROHNE OPTIMASS 1400C S25) measures the working fluid mass flow rate before the evaporator in both operation modes. In the evaporator (SWEP V200THx80, brazed plate type), the working fluid is evaporated and slightly superheated. In ORC mode, the working fluid is then directed to a high-performance oil-separator-collector (ESK Schultze BOS2-R-35F) where the lubrication oil (Reniso Triton CE 500) is separated from the vapour phase, which is consecutively passed into the expander. The expander is a modified twin-screw compressor (Bitzer OSK5361-K) originating from the refrigeration sector. The compressor has a built-in volume ratio of 3.1 and a swept volume of 0.678 L per rotation. The expander drives a 30 kW_{nom} synchronous reluctance motor (ABB M3BL 2000MLA 4) in generative mode. During

HTHP operation, the vapour from the evaporator is directly routed to the compressor, which is driven by the previously mentioned motor. In both operation modes, an inverter can adapt the motor speed, allowing for effective load control. The compressed high-temperature vapour is then passed through the oil separator before being put into the condenser (SWEP B200THx70, brazed plate type), where it liquefies and drains into the receiver. Analogously, the working fluid vapour after the expander in ORC mode is fully condensed in the condenser and drains into the receiver, closing the cycle. The rather complex piping around the oil separator and compressor stems from the mono-directional flow requirement of the oil separator. As indicated in Fig. 2, a multitude of PT100 class A temperature sensors and pressure transmitters (BD Sensors 17.620G) enable a close monitoring of the fluid states before and after most major components.

The oil separated from the working fluid vapour is collected in the oil-separator and fed into the test rig's oil system. Sufficient lubrication of the compressor (or expander) bearings and rotor profiles is the primary purpose of the oil system. The oil ensures proper functionality and longevity of the bearings. Moreover, it reduces friction losses of the rotors and seals the individual compression or expansion chambers by reducing leakage pathways inside the machine. After the separator, an oil pump (Verder VERDERGEAR VGS200) is installed and can be used in ORC mode to compensate for pressure losses in the oil system and ensure a sufficient flow rate towards the machine. In HTHP mode, the pump can be bypassed due to the pressure gradient produced by the compressor. Observations during the test rig commissioning indicated that the bypass can also be used in ORC mode without limiting the oil flow rate. Subsequently, an oil filter (Filtration Group Pi 2005, filter type Pi 3105 PS10) is passed to remove potentially harmful particles. Another brazed plate heat exchanger (SWEP BH3x50) cools down the oil before its injection onto the bearings. It is connected

to the primary cooling water line on the cold side, and the water flow rate can be controlled by the linear regulating valve V-59 (ESBE VLE122). In compressor mode, the complete oil stream is directed to the compressor and is internally divided into a stream for the bearings and one for the profiles (which is injected into the suction gas). This configuration is, of course, not useful in ORC operation, and the partial flow towards the compressor suction side (now being the expander exhaust) is closed by a solenoid valve. The small amount of oil required for rotor profile lubrication is ensured by the incomplete oil separation from the working fluid in ORC mode. If this is not sufficient, a part of the oil can be diverted between the oil pump and the oil cooler and injected into the expander suction stream. This flow path is shut off by a solenoid valve during HTHP operation and ORC operation if the oil separator efficiency is not too high. The total oil flow rate is measured by a Coriolis mass flow meter (RHEONIK RHM 06) and controlled by the regulating valve V-63 (Emerson EX5-U21). If necessary, the split ratio in ORC mode is calculated from an additional flow measurement in the branch towards the expander suction line and can be set by adjusting V-63. During commissioning, 3.5 kg of lubricant and roughly 33 kg of working fluid were filled into the test rig for the subsequent operation.

2.1.4. Control strategy

The test rig's two functionalities increase the complexity of the required control system compared to a mono-functional plant. The main control loops for both operation modes are depicted as dashed lines in Fig. 2. The red lines show the ORC control loops while blue is used for the HTHP mode. For both operation modes, the available heat source flow and temperature are considered as boundary conditions (c.f. Section 2.1.1) and are not part of the control strategy. In ORC mode, the superheating after the evaporator (T_{22}) was originally intended to be controlled by adapting the pump speed and, hence, the refrigerant mass flow rate. However, limitations of the working fluid pump led to a shift in the operational strategy, which is further discussed in Section 2.2.2. The evaporation pressure (p_{22}) is controlled by the expander speed, which is possible due to the use of a volumetric expansion machine. The condensation pressure (p_{25}) is controlled by adapting the mass flow rate of the primary cooling water using V-54. This determines the heat extracted from the main cycle and, hence, the condensation pressure for a given mass flow rate. Finally, the subcooling before the pump is controlled by an adaption of the tap water mass flow rate in the subcooler using V-51. In HTHP mode, the flow rate in the cooling circuit is set as a boundary condition by adapting the stroke of V-52. The water-side condenser inlet temperature (T_{43}) is controlled by the primary cooling water flow rate via V-54. The respective outlet temperature (T_{44}) is controlled by the compressor speed. The compressor speed influences both the refrigerant flow rate and the condensation pressure making a careful design of this control loop critical. The superheating after the evaporator (T_{22}) is controlled by the throttle valve V-38, which also has an impact on the overall process conditions. It becomes clear that the process parameters in HTHP mode are interdependent making a stable control more complex in this operation mode. The control loops for the oil system (as described in Section 2.1.3 already) are only indicated for ORC operation in Fig. 2 but are valid for HTHP operation as well.

2.2. Experimental procedure and evaluation

The HTHP and the ORC process should both be judged based on their general technical performance and in the context of their intended application scenario. Hence, the operational points evaluated for a general characterisation of the test rig are introduced first. Subsequently, the operation strategy and the relevant operational points for a geothermal CHP application are briefly discussed for both operation modes.

2.2.1. HTHP operation

To provide a general and abstract quantification of the HTHP's efficiency, a number of operating points with different thermal loads and temperature lifts is evaluated first. In this approach, a constant heat source temperature (T_{11}) of 75 °C and mass flow (\dot{m}_{HC}) of 2 kg/s are used. The ICC mass flow (\dot{m}_{ICC}) is then set to each of the values of 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 kg/s and for each mass flow the ICC supply temperature (T_{43}) is increased in steps of 5 °C while maintaining a ICC temperature lift ($\Delta T_{44,43}$) of 10 °C until operational limitations are reached. This effectively varies the HTHP's temperature lift for different thermal loads. Despite being a highly common process parameter in the evaluation of heat pump processes [2,27–29], different definitions of a heat pump's temperature lift are proposed in literature [12,30], often making it inherently difficult to compare different facilities. In this work, the temperature lift is defined as the difference of saturation temperatures at the respective condensation and evaporation pressure, as given in Eq. (1).

$$\Delta T_{\text{lift}} = T_{\text{sat}}(p_{\text{cond}}) - T_{\text{sat}}(p_{\text{evap}}) \quad (1)$$

This definition neglects the characteristics of the heat source and sink and allows for judging the actual HTHP performance. The observations yielded from this first general performance evaluation are further used for the plant evaluation according to the application scenario, which is subsequently described.

In a real geothermal CHP plant, the heat pump has to operate under strongly varying conditions. That includes varying temperature levels on both the heat source (geothermal brine) and heat sink (DHN) side and mass flow variations in the heat sink. Since the brine is first used to heat the DHN, its inlet temperature to the HTHP's evaporator can never be smaller than the DHN return temperature. For this study, a 5 K pinch in the brine-DHN heat exchanger is assumed and the heat source inlet temperature is hence always 5 K larger than the simulated DHN return. As the brine mass flow is constant in a real plant, at least during peak load times when the HTHP needs to be operated, only the simulated DHN mass flow (\dot{m}_{ICC}), its return temperature (T_{43}) and the temperature lift in the DHN ($\Delta T_{44,43}$) are varied in this study. The heat source mass flow is fixed at a value of 2 kg/s and an evaporator outlet superheating of 20 K is set for the working fluid in order to ensure complete evaporation and sufficient superheating before (and consequently also after) the compressor. Sufficient superheating of the working fluid vapour is required at the oil separator inlet to avoid working fluid absorption in the oil [31]. The mixing of working fluid with significantly colder oil in the compressor decreases the compressor outlet superheating, and the previously described (relatively large) superheating before the compressor helps to ensure sufficient outlet superheating.

The most important HTHP operational parameters are summarised on the left side of Table 1. The multiple combinations of heat sink (DHN) temperature levels and mass flows in Table 1 represent realistic load scenarios for an HTHP in the context of a geothermal GHP. The operational points are used to judge the load range of the present rHTHP and draw conclusions on its part- and full-load efficiency.

2.2.2. ORC operation

During ORC operation, the heat source mass flow usually shows significant fluctuations in a geothermal CHP plant. It is hence varied in a range between 0.5 kg/s and 1.5 kg/s in this study. Depending on the local geological conditions, the wellhead temperature of the brine can also vary. As discussed in detail by Molar-Cruz et al. the achievable wellhead temperatures for conventional geothermal heating projects can vary between 90 °C and 160 °C [32]. Therefore, this work investigates heat source temperatures of 110 °C and 130 °C, representing a typical characteristic of existing geothermal CHP plants in the Bavarian molasse basin [24]. In contrast to the HTHP operation, the brine is fed to the ORC directly from the wellhead and not cooled down by supplying heat to the DHN (c.f. Fig. 1). This explains the temperature

Table 1
Operational parameters for HTHP and ORC operation derived from a real application scenario.

HTHP operation		ORC operation	
Brine mass flow (\dot{m}_{HC}) in kg/s	2.0	Brine mass flow (\dot{m}_{HC}) in kg/s	0.5/1.0/1.5
Brine supply temperatures (T_{11}) in °C	55/75/95	Brine supply temperature (T_{11}) in °C	110/130
DHN mass flows (\dot{m}_{CC}) in kg/s	0.5/1.0/1.5	Evaporation pressure (p_{22}) in bar	7/8/9/10/11
DHN return temperatures (T_{13}) in °C	50/70/90	Condensation pressure (p_{25}) in bar	2.5
DHN temperature lifts in K	20/30	Pump inlet subcooling in K	15
Compressor inlet superheating in K	20	Working fluid pump speed in %	25/35/45

differences of the brine for both operation modes, given in Table 1. The evaporation pressure is usually a key optimisation parameter for ORC plants. For the first characterisation of the test rig, the evaporation pressure is varied in 1 bar steps between 7 bar and 11 bar for each heat source condition and working fluid pump speed, in order to evaluate its influence on the process efficiency. While it was originally planned to maintain a consistent expander inlet superheating for all operational points, this approach was discarded during plant commissioning. Strong vibrations of the working fluid pump currently limit its operation to a maximum of 50% of its rated maximum speed. Despite sufficient subcooling to avoid cavitation and consultation with the manufacturer, this issue could not be resolved, making it impossible to maintain the initially targeted superheating when high heat source mass flows meet low evaporation pressures. Hence, three different pump speeds (i.e. 25%, 35% and 45% of the maximum pump speed of 1800 rpm) are evaluated for each combination of heat source condition and evaporation pressure. The condensation pressure is usually minimised in practice in order to yield the maximum work output. In this study, it is set to 2.5 bar (yielding a condensation temperature of 44.7 °C) for the sake of repeatability, since the primary cooling water supply temperature (T_{45} , c.f. Fig. 2) sometimes fluctuates over the course of a day and within the year. In order to avoid pump cavitation, the pump inlet subcooling is set to a value of 15 K. This is required due to the low suction height of the pump and a high number of fittings in the connection line between the liquid collector and the pump inlet. Again, the relevant operational parameters are summarised on the right side of Table 1.

2.2.3. Data processing and evaluation

Measurement data from steady-state operational condition is required to evaluate the test rig's performance. Within the experimental campaigns conducted for this work, steady-state operation was assumed after the relevant temperature and pressure measurements in all subsystems showed constant values over an interval of five minutes, not accounting for small fluctuations caused by measurement noise and minor controller oscillations. In the post-processing routine, all measured values are averaged over an interval of ten minutes (after reaching steady-state operation) to yield the steady-state values. This aims at reducing the effect of measurement noise and the previously mentioned minor controller oscillations. Measured data includes the temperatures, pressures and mass (FR21/FR51) or volume (FR1/FR41) flow rates indicated in Fig. 2. Moreover, the motor/generator speed and torque for the reversible compressor can be obtained from the connected inverter. Also, the electrical consumption/generation of the inverters connected to the compressor and pump motors is measured. Finally, the fluid density of the working fluid/oil mixture and the (ideally) pure oil is measured in the Coriolis flow meters FR21 and FR51, respectively (c.f. Fig. 2).

The main control and data logging system of the test rig is implemented using the automation software *TwinCAT 3* by the manufacturer *Beckhoff Automation*. Due to its initial construction for a different test rig, the control software for the heating circuit is implemented in the automation software *LabVIEW™* by the manufacturer *National Instruments*. Communication between the two runtime instances is enabled by the ADS interface *TF3710 | TwinCAT 3 Interface for LabVIEW™*, provided by *Beckhoff Automation*. The measured values are subject to inaccuracies caused by the accuracy threshold of the respective sensors

and errors associated with signal processing and conversion after the sensor. Table 2 provides the absolute inaccuracies σ_i of the relevant sensors. The sensors are connected to analogue I/O modules from the manufacturers *Beckhoff Automation* and *National Instruments*, where the sensor output is converted into a 16 Bit integer value that is subsequently scaled to the respective range of the physical quantity for each sensor. Table 2 presents the accuracies of the relevant sensors while Table 3 summarises the inaccuracies introduced by the I/O modules. The detailed instrumentation of the heating circuit and its sensor and I/O module inaccuracies are presented in the work of Eyerer et al. [23].

For the performance evaluation, thermodynamic properties such as enthalpies, densities and entropies are required. These properties are calculated from the measured temperatures and pressures using the thermo-physical property database *Refprop 10* [33]. Where this is not possible (e.g. in the two-phase state after the HTHP expansion valve), the enthalpy is obtained by assuming isenthalpic state changes from a previous single-phase state (which is properly defined by temperature and pressure).

Due to the measurement inaccuracies discussed above, any quantity derived from the measured parameters also exhibits a certain error margin. This error is calculated based on the *Gaussian* error propagation given in Eq. (2).

$$\sigma_f = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1}\right)^2 \sigma_{x_1}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2}\right)^2 \sigma_{x_2}^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_n}\right)^2 \sigma_{x_n}^2} \quad (2)$$

This equation derives the absolute error σ_f of a parameter f based on the errors σ_{x_i} of its influencing parameters x_i . The errors of the performance metrics discussed in Section 2.3 and all required intermediate derived quantities are also determined by applying Eq. (2).

2.3. Performance indicators

In order to evaluate and explain the cycle performance presented in Section 3, adequate performance metrics for individual cycle components and the overall cycles are required. This section provides the performance metrics used in this work.

2.3.1. Component performance indicators

Especially the reversible compressor majorly influences the overall cycle efficiency. It can be characterised by different efficiency metrics, which are subsequently described. In general, many publications refer to isentropic efficiencies to characterise machine efficiencies. These efficiencies compare the real enthalpy change Δh_{real} of a conveyed fluid to the enthalpy change in an ideal isentropic (meaning adiabatic and fully reversible) process Δh_{is} . The isentropic efficiencies η_{is} for compressors and expanders are hence defined as

$$\eta_{\text{is,comp}} = \frac{\Delta h_{\text{is}}}{\Delta h_{\text{real}}} \quad \text{and} \quad (3)$$

$$\eta_{\text{is,exp}} = \frac{\Delta h_{\text{real}}}{\Delta h_{\text{is}}}, \quad (4)$$

respectively. In a strict thermodynamic sense, the application of isentropic efficiency metrics is limited to perfectly thermally insulated machines and thermal losses lead to flawed efficiency values. E.g. thermal losses on a compressor lead to lower exhaust gas temperatures and hence a lower Δh_{real} -value, resulting in unreasonably high efficiencies

Table 2
Measurement range and accuracy of the relevant sensors (according to the labels in Fig. 2).

Measured parameter	Sensors	Measurement principle	Range	Inaccuracy σ_i	Output
Temperature	T23, T26	PT100 class A	−200–600 °C	$\pm(2.2 + 0.002 \cdot T [^\circ\text{C}]) \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$	Resistance
	T11, T12	PT100 class AA	0–150 °C	$\pm(0.1 + 0.0017 \cdot T [^\circ\text{C}]) \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$	Resistance
	All others	PT100 class A	−200–600 °C	$\pm(0.15 + 0.002 \cdot T [^\circ\text{C}]) \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$	Resistance
Pressure	p43, p44	Strain gauge	0–16 bar	$\pm 0.224 \text{ bar}$	4...20 mA
	p45	Strain gauge	0–6 bar	$\pm 0.084 \text{ bar}$	4...20 mA
	p1, p2	Strain gauge	0–10 bar	$\pm 0.05 \text{ bar}$	4...20 mA
	All others	Strain gauge	0–16 bar	$\pm 0.128 \text{ bar}$	4...20 mA
Mass flow	FR21	Coriolis	0–5400 kg/h	$\pm 5.25 \text{ g/s}$	4...20 mA HART
	FR51	Coriolis	0.25–25 kg/min	$\pm(1.25 + 0.002 \cdot \dot{m} [\text{g/s}]) \text{ g/s}$	4...20 mA
Volume flow	FR41	Inductive	0–167 L/min	$\pm 0.835 \text{ L/min}$	4...20 mA
	FR1	Inductive	0–250 L/min	$\pm(0.005 \cdot \dot{V} [\text{L/min}] + 0.835) \text{ L/min}$	4...20 mA
Level	L21	Radar	0–6 m	$\pm 3 \text{ mm}$	4...20 mA HART
Torque	Inverter	n.a.	n.a.	$\pm 4\% \text{ of value}$	–

Table 3
Measurement inaccuracies of the test rig's I/O modules by the manufacturers *Beckhoff Automation* and *National Instruments* (e.o.r. = end of range; MV = measured value).

Module	I/O quantity	Resolution	Accuracy
Beckhoff EL3218	−200 to +850 °C (PT100 3 wire in)	16 Bit	$\pm 0,5 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$
Beckhoff EL3154	4...20 mA	16 Bit	$\pm 0,3\% \text{ e.o.r.}$
Beckhoff EL3112	0...20 mA	16 Bit	$\pm 0,3\% \text{ e.o.r.}$
Beckhoff EL3152	4...20 mA	16 Bit	$\pm 0,3\% \text{ e.o.r.}$
Beckhoff EL3182	0/4...20 mA (HART)	16 Bit	$\pm 0,3\% \text{ e.o.r.}$
Beckhoff EL4122	4...20 mA	16 Bit	$\pm 0,1\% \text{ e.o.r.}$
Beckhoff EL4124	4...20 mA	16 Bit	$\pm 0,1\% \text{ e.o.r.}$
Beckhoff EL3174	−10,73...+10,73 V or −21,47...+21,47 mA	16 Bit	$\pm 0,3\% \text{ e.o.r.}$
Beckhoff EL3443	480V, 1A (power measurement)	16 Bit	$\pm 0,6\% \text{ calculated value}$
NI 9208	−22...20 mA	16 Bit	$\pm(0.0076 \text{ MV} + 0.00908 \text{ mA})$
NI 9216	0...400 Ω	16 Bit	$\pm(0.00007 \text{ MV} + 0.1654 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C})$

which can exceed 100% if thermal losses are high. As the reversible compressor can only be thermally insulated to a limited extent, the application of isentropic efficiencies is impractical and different metrics are required.

For the reversible compressor, the mechanical η_{mech} is introduced for performance evaluation. It is defined as

$$\eta_{\text{mech,comp}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{wf}} \cdot \Delta h_{\text{su,ex}}}{P_{\text{sh,comp}}} \quad \text{and} \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_{\text{mech,exp}} = \frac{P_{\text{sh,exp}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{wf}} \cdot \Delta h_{\text{su,ex}}} \quad (6)$$

for compressors and expanders, respectively. In these equations, $\Delta h_{\text{su,ex}}$ represents the positive enthalpy change between the suction and exhaust port of the machine, \dot{m}_{wf} the conveyed working fluid mass flow and P_{sh} the positive mechanical shaft power. The latter is derived from the measured torque τ and the shaft speed n according to Eq. (7).

$$P_{\text{sh}} = 2\pi \cdot n \cdot \tau \quad (7)$$

The mechanical efficiency accounts for internal losses caused by friction, internal leakages and heat losses to the environment and is, hence, a good metric to judge the isolated machine performance. To quantify the influence of the drive train (consisting of motor and inverter), the electrical drive train efficiency $\eta_{\text{el,DT}}$ for HTHP and ORC operation is defined as

$$\eta_{\text{el,DT,HTHP}} = \frac{P_{\text{sh,comp}}}{P_{\text{el,motor}}} \quad \text{and} \quad (8)$$

$$\eta_{\text{el,DT,ORC}} = \frac{P_{\text{el,generator}}}{P_{\text{sh,exp}}}, \quad (9)$$

relating the electrical power consumption (for compressor operation) or power generation (for expander operation) of the inverter controlling the motor/generator to the respective mechanical shaft power of the twin-screw machine. It accounts for electrical losses in the motor/generator and inverter and allows drawing conclusions on the load dependent efficiencies of these components.

Internal leakages can be significant in twin-screw machines, calling for a suitable performance metric to evaluate their detrimental effect on the overall machine performance. Here, the volumetric efficiency is a well-established indicator. For the compressor, it is defined as

$$\eta_{\text{vol,comp}} = \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{su}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{su,id}}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{wf}}}{n_{\text{comp}} \cdot V_{\text{sw,comp}} \cdot \rho_{\text{su}}} \quad (10)$$

relating the actually conveyed suction side volume flow \dot{V}_{su} of the machine to the ideally conveyed volume flow without internal leakages $\dot{V}_{\text{su,id}}$ [34]. The latter can be derived from the machine's swept volume per shaft rotation V_{sw} and the respective machine speed n . For expanders, the filling factor FF is more common than the volumetric efficiency. It relates the actual conveyed mass flow to the ideal mass flow as shown by Eq. (11) [35].

$$FF = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{wf}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{su,id}}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{wf}}}{n_{\text{exp}} \cdot V_{\text{sw,exp}} \cdot \rho_{\text{su}}} \quad (11)$$

For a reversible compressor, the swept volumes of the compressor and expander are related by the built-in volume ratio r_{BV} according to the following equation:

$$V_{\text{sw,exp}} = \frac{V_{\text{sw,comp}}}{r_{\text{BV}}}. \quad (12)$$

2.3.2. Cycle performance indicators

The cycle performance of the HTHP and ORC are judged based on different metrics. For the HTHP, the performance is judged based on the coefficient of performance (COP), which is normally defined as the ratio of useful heat rejected in the condenser (\dot{Q}_{cond}) and the compressors electricity consumption ($P_{\text{el,comp}}$):

$$COP = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{cond}}}{P_{\text{el,comp}}}. \quad (13)$$

For geothermal ORC processes, there are two common approaches to evaluate the cycle performance: evaluating the ORC efficiency with respect to the actual transferred heat from the brine [36] or to the

theoretically available heat of the geothermal brine [24]. The net electrical thermal efficiency $\eta_{th,el,net}$ is defined as the ratio of net electrical power output $P_{el,net}$ (considering the working fluid pump's electricity consumption) and heat input to the evaporator \dot{Q}_{evap} , as defined in Eq. (14).

$$\eta_{th,el,net} = \frac{P_{el,net}}{\dot{Q}_{evap}} \quad (14)$$

However, a high thermal efficiency can also stem from a low heat source utilisation, resulting in a higher average evaporation temperature and hence an increased Carnot efficiency. Therefore, the thermal efficiency alone is of limited significance for applications that have a higher cost associated with their heat source, such as geothermal brine. For those applications, the net electrical system efficiency $\eta_{sys,el,net}$ has a higher practical relevance as it accounts for the heat source utilisation as well [37]. It is defined as the product of the net electrical thermal efficiency and the heat transfer efficiency η_{HT} :

$$\eta_{sys,el,net} = \eta_{th,el,net} \cdot \eta_{HT} = \frac{P_{el,net}}{\dot{Q}_{evap}} \cdot \frac{\dot{Q}_{evap}}{\dot{Q}_{HS}} \quad (15)$$

In this equation, the term \dot{Q}_{HS} defines the maximum available heat from the heat source, which can be extracted by cooling the heat source down to a reference temperature. This reference temperature is usually the cold reservoir temperature, explicitly the inlet temperature of the cooling medium. However, this work focuses on geothermal applications where the cooling medium is often air at temperatures in a range of -10°C to 30°C . As it is unrealistic to cool the geothermal brine to these temperature (for reasons of freezing and scaling), a reference temperature of 40°C is used in this work.

3. Results

The following chapter presents the results of the experimental test rig characterisation, starting with the HTHP operation and then moving on to the ORC operation. It provides insights into the general plant behaviour, highlighting the capabilities and limitations in both operational modes. The sections on HTHP and ORC performance both follow a clear structure: They begin by providing the most important performance indicators and process parameters to give the reader a perspective on the overall process performance. Subsequently, the trends in the aforementioned performance indicators are explained by detailed evaluations on a component level for the interested reader.

3.1. HTHP operation results

This section discusses the operational performance of the HTHP. It starts with the results of the HTHP's temperature lift variation in Section 3.1.1. These results are used to discuss and explain the general plant behaviour and specific effects during operation by analysing the individual components' performance. The observations yielded from this analysis are then further used in Section 3.1.2 to discuss the HTHP's capability to cover the operational range derived from its intended application.

3.1.1. Lift-dependent HTHP performance

For most heat pump applications, the availability of heat sources rises while their associated cost generally decreases when the heat source temperature level decreases. In contrast, the heat sink temperature is less flexible as it is mostly determined by the application. Hence, heat pumps that can achieve a high temperature lift while maintaining a reasonable COP are favourable, and the lift-dependent COP is a good metric to judge the quality of a heat pump. Of course, a high COP is of limited value if it can only be achieved at low heat duties. Therefore, the lift-dependent COP at different heat duties is the primary indicator to evaluate the HTHP's performance in this work. Fig. 3(a) shows the HTHP's COP for a temperature lift range between 25 K and 57 K at heat

sink mass flows of 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 kg/s, corresponding to heat duties of roughly 21, 43 and 63 kW (as indicated in Fig. 4(a)), respectively.

It is important to note that the condenser duty in Fig. 4(a) and all other subsequently discussed heat duties are calculated based on the water-side temperature change and mass flow in the relevant heat exchangers whenever possible. This is required as the presence of oil in the working fluid (and vice versa) can considerably change their thermodynamic behaviour, making calculations based on the working fluid side less reliable. As expected, the COP consistently decreases with rising temperature lifts (as defined in Eq. (1)) and reaches a maximum value of 6.4 at a lift of 25 K. The highest lift reached within this test row, i.e. with a heat source inlet temperature of 75°C , is 57 K, yielding a COP of approximately 3. For this heat source temperature, higher lifts are not possible due to temperature limitations in the primary cooling water line. Higher lifts could be achieved at lower heat source inlet temperatures, but the HTHP's efficiency and capacity are severely limited at low heat source temperatures due to the low evaporation pressures. This is discussed in more detail in the subsequent Section 3.1.2.

Looking at Fig. 4(a), a gradual increase in the additionally required electrical compressor power can be observed for each step. This phenomenon is discussed in Appendix A.1.1 in the Appendix for the sake of brevity of this section.

The relative distance of the COP curves in Fig. 3(a) can mostly be explained by a combination of two effects, specifically the electrical drive-train efficiency and the influence of heat losses. Fig. 3(b) shows the mechanical COP, using compressor shaft power instead of electrical power in Eq. (13). For the mechanical COP, the COP curves for the upper two heat duties are nearly congruent, and the offset of the curve for the lowest heat load is reduced. This can be explained by the electrical efficiency of the drive-train (including motor and inverter), which is depicted in Fig. 5(b).

As expected for most electrical machines, decreasing motor speeds lead to a decline in efficiency. For the highest two thermal loads, the motor operates at reasonably large speeds and the electrical efficiency (which is very high in this speed range) only differs slightly, explaining the small difference between mechanical COP and regular COP for these curves. For smaller motor speeds, the efficiency is naturally lower, but the effect of decreasing torque is also more pronounced. In contrast to the upper two thermal loads, the electrical efficiency for the lowest thermal load strongly declines with decreasing temperature lift, indicating a strong dependence on torque in this speed range. As a result, significantly smaller electrical efficiencies are yielded for the smallest thermal load on average, explaining the comparatively larger difference between mechanical COP and regular COP. The remaining offset between the mechanical COP curves in Fig. 3(b) can mostly be explained by the relative impact of heat losses. Using average values of the respective heat loss curves depicted in Fig. 4(b), the heat losses are equal to 34.1%, 19.2% and 13.9% of the condenser duty for the lowest, intermediate and highest heat load, respectively. This large share of heat losses has a major deteriorating effect on the COP for the smallest heat load, as a significant share of energy input is lost to the environment. The large error margin of the heat losses depicted in Fig. 4(b) stems from its calculation via an energy balance around the whole test rig, but a detailed explanation of this matter is provided in Appendix A.1.2 of the Appendix for the sake of brevity.

The previous two paragraphs explain why the COP curve for the lowest thermal duty (i.e. the red curve in Fig. 3) is significantly lower compared to the other two curves. However, the small difference in relative heat losses for the highest two thermal duties would indicate a further increase in COP values for the highest duty. The same applies to the marginal increase in drive-train efficiency for the highest duty compared to the middle one (c.f. blue and green curves in the above figures). This expected minor increase in COP for the highest duty is compensated by the much higher pressure losses in the oil separator. The pressure losses in the oil separator (depicted in Fig. 6) are by far

Fig. 3. Electrical (a) and mechanical (b) coefficient of performance of the HTHP for the temperature lift evaluation.

Fig. 4. Thermal condenser duties (a) and total heat losses (b) of the HTHP for the temperature lift evaluation.

Fig. 5. Electrical drive-train efficiency of the HTHP for the temperature lift evaluation.

the largest pressure losses in the cycle and are hence investigated in more detail subsequently.

The oil separator pressure losses slightly decline with higher working fluid mass flow rates for the lowest and highest heat duty, even though a higher flow rate would intuitively imply larger pressure losses. This results from the higher gas density after the compressor caused by an increasing condensation pressure, which leads to an overall small change in the volumetric flow rate entering the oil separator (c.f. Fig. 6(b)) and consequently small changes in pressure losses. The inconsistent behaviour of the curve for the intermediate heat load ($\dot{m}_{\text{DHN}} = 1.0$ kg/s) is discussed below, and later on together with the

behaviour of the compressor’s volumetric efficiency. In general, also for this curve, the oil separator pressure loss mostly behaves as expected. In this context, it is important to note that the data points in the green and red curves in Fig. 6 depict increasing temperature lifts (and compressor speeds) when being followed from left to right. The blue curve, in contrast, has the lowest temperature lift on its right end and needs to be followed from right to left (and right again for Fig. 6(a)) when the temperature lift increases. The reason for this inconsistency is explained later in this work, together with the compressor’s volumetric efficiency. For the intermediate heat load, the largest mass flow rates are observed at the lowest temperature lifts and, consequently, the lowest condensation pressures, which leads to initially high volumetric flow rates and pressure losses. With increasing compressor speed and decreasing mass flow rate, the pressure loss declines. At some point, the mass flow rate starts to increase again, but the previously described effect of stagnating volumetric flow rates comes into play and results in a minor decrease in oil separator pressure loss.

There is no obvious explanation for the decreasing pressure loss despite relatively constant volumetric flow rates. The most likely explanation is a reduction in gas and oil viscosity at the oil separator inlet caused by the higher compressor outlet temperatures that come along with the increasing mass flows. However, as this includes highly complex geometries and multi-phase flow, there is no way to examine the phenomenon at a reasonable effort, and it will hence not be evaluated in more detail. As stated above, overall higher oil separator pressure losses further increase the compressor duty and lower the COP for higher heat duties, which becomes especially important for the large pressure losses at the highest duty. Finally, the decrease in the oil separator pressure loss curves could explain the slightly reducing slope of the COP curves in Fig. 3.

Fig. 6. Oil separator pressure loss of the HTHP over oil separator inlet working fluid mass flow rate (a) and volume flow rate (b) of the HTHP for the temperature lift evaluation.

As already mentioned above, the mass flow for the intermediate thermal load in Fig. 6(a) does not behave consistently with the other two load curves when the temperature lift (and consequently the compressor speed) are increased. The behaviour is reproducible and, hence, flawed measurements can be ruled out. Consequently, this behaviour is examined in detail to find an explanation for the counter-intuitive plant behaviour. The volumetric efficiency of the compressor is the most important parameter influencing the conveyed mass flow in a heat pump for otherwise fixed boundary conditions. In literature, the compressor speed and the absolute pressure difference are introduced as the most important impact factors on volumetric efficiency. As the driving force for internal leakages, an increasing pressure difference usually leads to lower volumetric efficiencies at a constant speed. In contrast, an increasing compressor speed at a constant pressure difference normally increases volumetric efficiency as the leakage remains constant and the total conveyed mass flow increases, effectively reducing the relative impact of internal leakages. Another important influence is the amount of oil introduced into the compressor. It needs to be sufficient to lubricate the rotor profiles properly, sealing the individual compression chambers against each other and reducing leakages in the process. Moreover, proper lubrication is required to reduce friction losses in the compressor.

Fig. 7 shows the volumetric compressor efficiency depending on the three previously mentioned parameters. Again, the curve for the intermediate heat load is not consistent with the other two curves. While a major increase in volumetric efficiency is observed for the lowest and highest heat load with increasing compressor speed as expected, the volumetric efficiency drops sharply from a high initial value before rising again at a certain compressor speed for the intermediate heat load (c.f. Fig. 7(a)). For low compressor speeds the benefit of rising speed seems to be more pronounced than for higher speeds, as the volumetric efficiency increases much sharper within a relatively narrow speed range in Fig. 7(a).

In general, when the profiles receive a sufficient amount of oil for the respective compressor speed, ensuring proper sealing of the compression chamber, the beneficial effect of increased speed outweighs the detrimental effect of larger pressure differences. This is confirmed by Fig. 7(b), where the volumetric efficiency increases despite a considerable increase in pressure difference for the lowest and highest thermal load. The higher values of volumetric efficiency for the lowest heat load compared to the highest one, despite smaller compressor speeds, imply that lubrication efficiency is better for the lowest heat load, and more oil should be fed into the compressor for higher speeds.

The behaviour of the intermediate load curve is more complex and requires consideration of the effect of all three previously mentioned influence parameters. The key to understanding it is the oil lubrication of the screw profiles. As depicted in Fig. 7(a) the oil mass flow towards

the compressor (FR51 in Fig. 2) was kept at a constant rate of around 15 g/s for the lower two load curves and then increased step-wise for the high compressor speeds of the highest load curve. At the beginning of the intermediate load curve, the beneficial effects of a small pressure difference, an already reasonably high compressor speed and sufficient lubrication for the respective speed are superposed, resulting in a very high volumetric efficiency. Consequently, the conveyed mass flow is very high. With increasing compressor speed and constant (rather low) oil mass flow, the lubrication efficiency seems to deteriorate quickly, leading to a steep decline of the volumetric efficiency and the conveyed mass flow (c.f. Figs. 7(a) and 6(a)). With further increasing speed, the detrimental effects of insufficient lubrication and rising pressure differences are outweighed by the benefits of increasing speed, causing the volumetric efficiency to rise again slowly. However, due to the insufficient lubrication, the volumetric efficiency remains low compared to the other two load curves. The previous explanation implies a tipping point, where a constant oil mass flow becomes insufficient to seal the compression chambers at a rising compressor speed. To validate this, a variation of the compressor speed was conducted at a constant oil mass flow of 22 g/s for pressure ratios of 2 and 3, respectively. For the sake of brevity at this point, the respective results and implications are discussed in Appendix A.1.3 in the Appendix for the interested reader. Appendix A.1.4 further discusses potential methodical errors in the calculation of the volumetric compressor efficiency that are associated with incomplete oil separation and the associated presence of oil in the compressor suction gas.

Finally, the mechanical efficiency of the compressor depicted in Fig. 8 shows a very similar behaviour as the volumetric efficiency from Fig. 7(b). While the low mechanical efficiencies at low pressure ratios could be explained by the effect of over-compression, no maximum is observed at pressure ratios around the built-in volume ratio, and the efficiency shows a continuous rise. This implies that the volumetric efficiency is the dominating influence on the mechanical efficiency, outweighing the effect of under-compression for higher pressure ratios. The mechanical efficiency curve for the intermediate heat load, which shows no reasonable dependency on the pressure ratio, further supports this argument. Higher compressor speeds usually lead to a minor decline in mechanical efficiency due to increased friction losses. However, the significantly higher values for the lowest heat load curve also imply that the volumetric efficiency is the dominant factor here.

In conclusion, the previously discussed results show that the present reversible HTHP is able to operate as an HTHP within a wide load range, providing relatively high temperature lifts at good COP values. The obtained COP values align well with reported performance data from Jeßberger et al. [38], Weitzer et al. [14], and Dumont et al. [3], who also measured COPs between 3 and 7 for the investigated temperature lift range. The choice of a reluctance motor for the drive-train is

Fig. 7. Volumetric compressor efficiency and oil mass flow over compressor speed (a) and volumetric efficiency over pressure difference (b) of the HTHP for the temperature lift evaluation.

Fig. 8. Mechanical compressor efficiency of the HTHP for the temperature lift evaluation.

validated by high electrical efficiencies, contributing to high part-load efficiency. For further studies, special focus should be put on identifying the optimal oil dosage for different compressor speeds, as it has a massive impact on the volumetric efficiency. The derived knowledge about this is considered in the operational characterisation according to the intended application scenario, which is presented subsequently in Section 3.1.2. Moreover, a larger oil separator could help to ensure better oil separation and reduce pressure losses, which will further increase the HTHP's efficiency. Finally, better thermal insulation could also boost performance at low thermal loads.

3.1.2. Application-based HTHP evaluation

As discussed in Section 2.2.1, the results presented in this section seek to determine how flexible and efficient the rHTHP test rig can operate within its intended application scenario, i.e. a geothermal heating plant. As the general plant behaviour observed during the application-based evaluation shows many redundancies to the previously described behaviour from Section 3.1.1, only some key performance characteristics are presented subsequently. A detailed analysis of the respective operating points is provided for the interested reader in Appendix A.2 of the Appendix. Table A.1 presents the relevant operating points identified for this evaluation approach and indicates the experimental feasibility of the respective points together with the most relevant plant parameters during operation. The operation points with no indicated limitation were feasible, while the ones without any values and indicated limitation were not achieved due to different constraints and limitations of the test rig. The remaining points, where the actually achieved ΔT_{ICC} is given in brackets, were not feasible to the full extent

but can still be considered relevant due to the proximity to the intended plant state.

In addition to Table A.1, the COP values are depicted over the temperature lift in Fig. 9(a) with numbering according to the last column of Table A.1. The numbering of the data points is included in all graphs of this section (and the more detailed discussion in Appendix A.2) for the sake of clarity. Besides the COP, the respective thermal duties of the HTHP are depicted in Fig. 9(b) to show the operational flexibility of the HTHP. The observed thermal duties between roughly 40 kW and 110 kW prove that the HTHP is capable of operating highly flexibly while maintaining consistently good COPs above 3.5 under realistic load conditions. While a general trend of declining COPs with rising temperature lift can be observed in Fig. 9(a) in agreement with the results of Section 3.1.1, some outliers to this trend are observed for small temperature lift. This is mostly caused by strongly reduced volumetric efficiencies or low drive-train efficiencies for the respective points. As stated before, a more detailed discussion of this is provided in Appendix A.2 in the Appendix.

In conclusion, most observations made in Section 3.1.1 are confirmed by this second approach to characterising the test rig. The oil delivery to the compressor and its effect on the volumetric efficiency should be further evaluated to enhance the plant capacity, especially at low heat source temperatures. Moreover, a larger oil separator will improve the overall plant efficiency by reducing pressure losses and allow for higher temperature lifts of the HTHP. The latter is enabled by reducing the difference between the compressor outlet pressure and the condensation pressure, requiring lower compressor speeds for comparable condensation pressures. As the condensation pressure is directly linked to the heat sink outlet temperature by the small condenser pinch (c.f. Appendix A.1.1 and Fig. A.1), larger heat sink temperatures can be achieved before the compressor speed limit is reached. Once a larger oil separator is installed, a larger throttle valve could enhance the plant efficiency at high heat source temperatures. As seen for points 16 and 17 in Table A.1, the throttle partially operated at maximum stroke, leading to an increased superheating of 21 K and 26 K after the evaporator, respectively. While this does not necessarily limit the capacity, it decreases the cycle efficiency. Generally, the proposed design is well suited to operate as a HTHP for peak load coverage in a geothermal heating plant as satisfying COP values are obtained for a relatively wide range of realistic operating conditions.

3.2. ORC operation results

As described in Section 2.2.2, the ORC is tested using a variety of operational points which represent its wide operational range when applied in a geothermal CHP plant. This includes variations in heat source mass flow and supply temperature. Consequently, three different

Fig. 9. Coefficient of performance (a) and thermal duty (b) of the HTHP for application-based evaluation.

Fig. 10. Net electric thermal efficiency for a heat source mass flow of 0.5 kg/s (a) and 1.0 kg/s (b) for ORC operation.

heat source mass flows (0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 kg/s) are tested at inlet temperatures of 110 °C and 130 °C each. For each of these heat source conditions the working fluid pump speed is varied, operating at 25%, 35% and 45% of its maximum allowed speed. While the lower speed limit is chosen to ensure sufficient oil delivery to the oil separator (avoiding dry running of the expander), the maximum speed is constrained by increasing vibrations of the pump. For each pump speed, the evaporation pressure is then varied in steps of 1 bar between 7 bar and 11 bar while keeping a constant condensation pressure of 2.5 bar. In some cases, not all evaporation pressures are possible, as they would violate the required minimum expander inlet superheating of 10 K or the minimum expander speed of 500 rpm. This procedure yields a total number of 69 valid operating points, which are subsequently discussed. The Figs. 10 and 11(a) show the net electric thermal efficiency (c.f. Eq. (14)) of the ORC for the previously described operating conditions.

Some general trends can be observed here. With rising heat source mass flows the cycle efficiency slightly declines for all pump speeds and evaporation pressures in the working fluid cycle. This can most likely be attributed to lower cooling of the heat source and, consequently, more exergy destruction in the evaporator by a higher average temperature difference. This is supported by Fig. 11(b), which shows a $T-Q$ -diagram for the respective maximum efficiency operating point of each heat source mass flow. The total heat transfer in the evaporator is very similar due to the same working fluid mass flow rate, the same evaporation and condensation pressure and the shared subcooling and superheating before and after the evaporator. What majorly differs is the respective heat source outlet temperature, leading to significant differences in exergy destruction and hence thermal efficiency. Another general trend in the thermal efficiencies are the (mostly) slightly lower efficiency

values for the heat source temperature of 110 °C. This can be explained by the lower average temperature difference between heat source and heat sink, reducing the Carnot efficiency and thereby also the thermal efficiency of the cycle. Other parameters such as the working fluid mass flow or the pressure ratios over the expander are similar for the respective operating points with both heat source temperature levels and hence cannot explain the differences observed for different heat source temperatures.

The heat source utilisation, determined by its outlet temperature after the evaporator, is also the reason for the considerable differences in system efficiency according to Eq. (15). Fig. 12(a) shows the system efficiencies at different heat source conditions for a pump speed of 45%, as this pump speed consistently yields the highest thermal efficiencies.

The maximum observed system efficiency significantly drops from roughly 2.6% over 1.4% to 0.99% for heat source mass flows of 0.5 kg/s, 1.0 kg/s and 1.5 kg/s, respectively. As indicated in Eq. (15), the system efficiency is the product of the net electric thermal efficiency and the heat transfer efficiency with the latter being the ratio of evaporator duty and the maximum heat obtainable from the heat source. The thermal efficiencies of the operating points depicted in Fig. 12(a) do not majorly differ at comparable pressure ratios (c.f. Figs. 10 and 11(a)) and hence cannot explain the significant differences in system efficiencies. The deviations must thus be explained by the heat transfer efficiency. When the heat source temperature, the working fluid pump speed, pump inlet subcooling and the pressure levels are kept constant in the ORC, the evaporator duty stays fairly constant as well. This results in a relatively constant numerator of the heat transfer efficiency, while its denominator decreases proportionally with lower heat source mass flows, leading to an increasing system efficiency. This behaviour

Fig. 11. Net electric thermal efficiency for a heat source mass flow of 1.5 kg/s (a) and evaporator T-Q-diagram for the most efficient operating points at different heat source flows (b) for ORC operation.

Fig. 12. System efficiency for a working fluid pump speed of 45% (a) and thermal as well as heat transfer efficiency at varying heat source mass flow (b) for ORC operation.

is depicted in Fig. 12(b) using the operating points with a pressure ratio of roughly three from Fig. 12(a).

In contrast to the thermal efficiencies, the operating points with lower heat source temperatures consistently yield higher system efficiencies. This can again be attributed to the heat transfer efficiency. As a result of the oversized evaporator, the working fluid mostly leaves the evaporator with a temperature close to the heat source inlet temperature. With otherwise unchanged cycle parameters in the ORC, this results in a slightly higher evaporator duty at higher heat source temperatures due to the higher sensitive heat uptake during superheating. However, the sensitive heat of the working fluid vapour is relatively small compared to the sensitive heat of water. This leads to a disproportional increase of the heat transfer efficiency's denominator with rising heat source temperatures, reducing the overall system efficiency. This is confirmed by Fig. 12(b), where the heat transfer efficiencies of the operating points at a heat source temperature of 110 °C are consistently slightly higher than those at 130 °C.

The general trends of thermal efficiency and system efficiency can further be explained by the efficiency curve of the expander, its filling factor and the pressure losses in the oil separator. Thermal and system efficiency display a maximum at pressure ratios between 3 and 3.5, which matches the expander's BVR of 3.1. Neglecting temperature influences, the pressure ratio roughly translates to the applied volume ratio of the expander (i.e. the ratio of the specific gas volume of exhaust gas and suction gas). When the applied volume ratio matches the BVR, no under- or over-expansion losses occur, and the expander exhibits its maximum efficiency. This behaviour is confirmed by the mechanical

expander efficiencies, which are provided for a heat source mass flow of 1.0 kg/s in Fig. 13(a). As expected, the maximum efficiency is yielded for pressure ratios around the BVR value of 3.1. A detailed discussion and explanation of the mechanical efficiency, the filling factor and pressure losses in the oil separator offers little additional value for the overall plant performance evaluation and is therefore provided in Appendix A.3 for the interested reader.

The electric power output from the generator is influenced by many of the previously discussed process parameters and loss mechanisms, but also by the frequency- and torque-dependent electrical efficiency of the generator-inverter train. For the sake of brevity, these effects are not discussed in greater detail. The interested reader can find the generator's gross electricity output (already considering inverter losses) for different working fluid pump speeds and an efficiency map of the drive-train in ORC mode in Figs. A.6 and A.7 in the Appendix. Within the investigated range of heat source mass flows and pump speeds, electric powers between 1.33 kW and 5.69 kW are yielded. As expected, a strong decline in generated power can be observed with lower pump speeds and, accordingly, lower working fluid mass flow rates. Moreover, low pressure ratios generally yield significantly lower power output due to the lower expander shaft torque and over-expansion losses. Finally, a significant decline in electricity generation is observed for larger pressure ratios at lower pump speeds, as the associated low expander speeds come along with relatively low electrical drive-train efficiencies. In contrast to the heat source temperature, which has a major impact on the generator power output, the heat source mass flow shows little effect.

Fig. 13. Mechanical expander efficiency at $\dot{m}_{\text{HC}} = 1.0 \text{ kg/s}$ (a) and filling factor of the expander (b) for ORC operation.

To conclude, the ORC operation was evaluated under a wide range of operating conditions with respect to heat source and working fluid cycle conditions. The cycle consistently yields good net electric thermal efficiencies around 5–6% for the highest working fluid pump speed at different heat source conditions. The net electric system efficiency is constrained to maximum values of 2.5% with the heat source conditions (max. 130°C) and reference temperature of 40°C in this work. These values align well with literature values for ORC efficiency that are reported for similar heat source and heat sink conditions. In particular, Dumont et al. [3] obtain net electric thermal efficiencies between 1% and 5% for similar heat source conditions, while Dawo [37] reports system efficiencies between 1% and 2% for a heat source temperature of 120°C . Both thermal and especially system efficiency could be improved by higher working fluid mass flow rates, which requires a higher working fluid pump capacity. The overall cycle efficiency is dominated by the Carnot efficiency and the mechanical expander efficiency, while oil separator pressure losses seem to play a subordinate role. Nonetheless, the oil separator should be replaced by a larger version to ensure proper oil separation and simultaneously reduce pressure losses.

4. Conclusion

This paper presents the first experimental investigation of a scalable rHTHP plant, judging its technical feasibility and efficiency for geothermal CHP applications. A major benefit of the proposed plant concept is the reversible use of all cycle components (whenever possible), yielding the highest potential for economic viability among all similar plant concepts proposed in the literature. The test rig is connected to a hot water circuit with a nominal heating power of 200 kW, acting as a heat source with variable supply temperature and mass flow for both operation modes. The test rig can either operate in ORC mode, converting heat at variable temperatures into electricity, or as a high-temperature heat pump, supplying heat to a simulated district heating network (in form of an intermediate cooling circuit) at elevated temperature levels.

The HTHP operation of the test rig is first analysed by varying the heat pump's temperature lift at different thermal loads to gain insights on its general efficiency and operating behaviour. At a constant heat source temperature of 75°C and thermal duties of 21 kW, 43 kW and 63 kW, temperature lifts between 25 K and 57 K are achieved, yielding COP values between 6.4 and 3. Without temperature limitations of the in-house cooling water line, higher temperature lifts would be possible. In a second approach to characterise the heat pump's capacity and operational limitations, heat source temperatures of 55°C , 75°C and 95°C are set, while the DHN return temperature is set to 50°C , 70°C and 90°C for the respective heat source temperatures. The thermal load in the simulated DHN is varied between 42 kW and 110 kW at DHN temperature glides of 20 K and 30 K by variation of DHN mass

flow. This approach seeks to mimic realistic load conditions for the application in a geothermal CHP plant. In general, the heat pump can mostly supply the required heat at the specified temperature glides for a heat source temperature of 95°C , while its capacity is partially or severely limited by compressor speed and oil separator pressure loss for lower heat source temperatures. This is mainly caused by low volumetric compressor efficiencies which are most likely rooted in insufficient lubrication. Moreover, the oil separator is too small in the current design, leading to insufficient oil separation and high pressure losses, which especially affects the plant performance at low heat source temperatures due to the lower gas densities. While the heat pump shows good COP values over a considerable range of temperature lifts and is able to deliver a wide range of thermal duties, further experiments and improvements to the plant design are proposed. A larger oil separator should be installed to enhance plant efficiency and enable higher temperature lifts as well as larger thermal duties by reducing pressure losses. Moreover, the optimal oil supply to the compressor should be analysed carefully, as optimal lubrication seems to require rigorous adaption of the oil delivery with rising compressor speeds.

The ORC operation of the test rig is analysed by operation at varying heat source mass flows of 0.5 kg/s, 1.0 kg/s and 1.5 kg/s and heat source temperatures of 110°C and 130°C . For each heat source condition, the working fluid pump speed is adapted in three steps and a variation of the evaporation pressure between 7 bar and 11 bar is performed at each pump speed. By keeping a constant condensation pressure of 2.5 bar, the optimal pressure ratio and pump speed are identified for each of the previously described heat source conditions. Maximum net electric thermal efficiencies of 5–6% are consistently achieved for the highest pump speed and pressure ratios around 3.5 for all heat source mass flows. This is caused mainly by adapted expansion in the twin-screw expander and optimal heat source cooling in the evaporator. Considering the heat source utilisation, system efficiencies between 0.8% and 2.5% are achieved for the different heat source mass flows. The system efficiency can be further increased by installing a working fluid pump with a larger capacity, enabling further cooling of the heat source at larger mass flows. While it does not majorly affect the ORC's efficiency, the undersized oil separator strongly affects the test rig's part load capability and oil supply to the expander. Due to a low separation efficiency, a sufficient oil level can only be maintained by larger working fluid flow rates. A larger oil separator is hence required to ensure sufficient oil delivery to the expander bearings at higher rotational speeds and low working fluid mass flow rates.

In summary, while some operational challenges and potential design improvements remain (as discussed above), the proposed rHTHP design is overall well-suited to function effectively as an HTHP for peak load coverage in a geothermal CHP plant, achieving satisfactory COP values during HTHP operation and net efficiencies during ORC operation across a relatively broad spectrum of realistic operating conditions.

Nomenclature

Abbreviations		Latin symbols	
CHP	Combined heat and power	f	Parameter for error calculation, –
COP	Coefficient of performance	FF	Filling factor, –
DHN	District heating network	h	Specific enthalpy, J/kg
e.o.r.	End of range	\dot{m}	Mass flow, kg/s or g/s
HC	Heating circuit	n	Rotational speed, rpm or Hz
HEX	Heat exchanger	p	Pressure, Pa
HTHP	High temperature heat pump	P	Power, W
ICC	Intermediate cooling circuit	\dot{Q}	Heat flow, W
MV	Measured value	r	Ratio, –
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle	T	Temperature, K or °C
P&ID	Piping and instrumentation diagram	v	Specific volume, m ³ /kg
PTES	Pumped thermal electricity storage	V	Volume, m ³
rHTHP	Reversible high temperature heat pump	\dot{V}	Volumetric flow rate, m ³ /s or L/s
TSC	Twin-screw compressor	x	Influencing parameter, –
Subscripts		Greek symbols	
amb	Ambient	Δ	Difference, –
BV	Built-in volume	η	Efficiency, – or %
comp	Compressor	ρ	Density, kg/m ³
cond	Condenser	σ	Absolute error, –
DT	Drive train	τ	Torque, Nm
el	Electrical		
evap	Evaporator		
ex	Exhaust side		
exp	Expander		
gen	Generator		
HS	Heat source		
HT	Heat transfer		
id	Ideal		
is	Isentropic		
loss	Heat losses		
mech	Mechanical		
OS	Oil separator		
p	Pressure		
real	For real state change		
sat	Saturation		
sh	Shaft		
su	Suction side		
sw	Swept		
sys	System		
th	Thermal		
vol	Volumetric		
wf	Working fluid		

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Florian Kaufmann: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jannik von Zabienski:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Leon von Ribbeck:** Investigation, Data curation. **Moritz Ehmann:** Investigation, Data curation. **Hartmut Spliethoff:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Christopher Schiffler:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

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Appendix

This section provides some additional experimental observations and explanations that are not included in the main script for the sake of clarity and brevity. It is aimed at interested readers who are interested in understanding the detailed mechanistic behaviour and limitations of the test rig on a component level.

A.1. Supplementary material: Lift-based HTHP evaluation

The following subsections discuss operational behaviour and phenomena that were observed during the lift-based HTHP evaluation, but were excluded from Section 3.1.1 for the sake of clarity and brevity.

A.1.1. Increasing surplus motor power for rising temperature lifts

Looking at Fig. 4(a), a gradual increase in the additionally required electrical compressor power can be observed for each step. The effect is more pronounced for higher thermal loads and can most likely be attributed to the rising working fluid mass flow rates with each step of the temperature lift (c.f. Fig. 6(a)). During operation, it was observed that the condenser is rather oversized for the heat loads achieved in this study. This leads to very small pinch points in the condenser, and an increase in the heat sink's temperature directly results in an increase in condensation temperature and, hence, also condensation pressure as shown in Fig. A.1. The rising condensation pressure not only leads to an increase in compressor duty but also lowers the latent heat of condensation, requiring a higher working fluid mass flow to yield a constant heat duty in the condenser. The increased mass flow again causes an increased compressor duty, leading to the gradual rise in additional compressor duty mentioned above. Two other effects, which most likely further amplify this phenomenon, are the much higher pressure losses in the oil separator (c.f. Fig. 6) and higher overall heat losses for the load curves with higher heat duties as depicted in Fig. 4(b).

A.1.2. Large error margins of the heat losses

The large error margin of the heat losses depicted in Fig. 4(b) stems from its calculation via an energy balance around the whole test rig. The heat duties of evaporator and condenser, which are used in this energy balance, are based on the water-side temperature and flow measurement. Due to the high heat capacity of water and despite reasonable measurement accuracy for the temperatures, this approach leads to relatively large error margins in the calculated heat flows when the Gaussian error propagation according to Eq. (2) is applied. The already considerable error margins of the individual heat duties are further amplified when the Gaussian error propagation is applied to the energy balance equation, resulting in the large error margins depicted for the heat losses in Fig. 4(b).

Fig. A.1. Condenser T-Q-diagrams for $\dot{m}_{\text{DHN}} = 1.0 \text{ kg/s}$ of the HTHP for the temperature lift evaluation.

Fig. A.2. Volumetric compressor efficiency over compressor speed for the temperature lift evaluation.

A.1.3. Speed-dependent lubrication goodness

To validate the thesis of a compressor speed tipping point, which is marked by a drastic decline in sealing capabilities for a constant oil mass flow and accordingly a sharp decline in volumetric compressor efficiency, a variation of the compressor speed at a constant oil mass flow of 22 g/s for pressure ratios of 2 and 3, respectively, is conducted. The results are presented in Fig. A.2.

By keeping the pressure ratio constant, the pressure difference is mostly ruled out as an impact factor on the volumetric efficiency. As previously described, the volumetric efficiency for a pressure ratio of two in Fig. A.2 first makes a sharp increase (consistent with Fig. 7(a)), before declining sharply at a compressor speed of roughly 1400 rpm. Since the beneficial effect of increasing speed remains, this strong decrease in volumetric efficiency can only be explained by a decline in the lubrication efficiency, potentially due to a ripped oil film caused by faster rotation of the screw profiles (and accordingly higher shear forces on the oil film). The curve for a pressure ratio of three further confirms the previously made statements. Starting at lower initial values, caused by the higher pressure difference, the volumetric efficiency declines with rising compressor speed as a result of insufficient lubrication. Similar to the intermediate load curve in Fig. 7, the detrimental effect of insufficient lubrication is outweighed by the benefits of further increasing compressor speeds at some point, causing the volumetric efficiency to rise slowly again.

A.1.4. Methodical flaws in volumetric efficiency calculation

Of course, volumetric efficiency values larger than 100% in Fig. A.2 make no sense from a physical perspective. Hence, the calculations

were properly checked but no mistake could be found. The explanation for these high values is an incomplete separation in the oil separator, causing an unknown amount of oil to be dragged along the cycle and to be included in the mass flow measurement FR21 (c.f. Fig. 2). The decreasing oil separation efficiency is caused by increasing volumetric flow rates in the oil separator, as the higher flow velocity through the separator mesh promotes the entrainment of oil droplets from the mesh. Since the volumetric efficiency is calculated under the assumption that FR21 measures pure working fluid, the presence of oil leads to a flawed increase in the calculated volumetric suction flow rate of the compressor used in Eq. (10). However, the qualitative explanations derived from Fig. A.2 remain valid and unaffected by the absolute values of the volumetric efficiency. The incomplete oil separation is a result of an unintentionally under-designed system, which is also confirmed by the high oil separator pressure losses. The manufacturer proposes a maximum pressure loss of 0.8 bar if the oil separator is operated within its intended range.

A.2. Supplementary material: Application-based HTHP evaluation

This section provides a more detailed discussion of the application-based HTHP evaluation in addition to what is already discussed in Section 3.1.2. Table A.1 summarises the relevant operating points (feasible and unfeasible) for this evaluation approach.

It is clearly visible in Table A.1 that the number of feasible operating points increases with higher heat source temperatures. This can mainly be attributed to the speed limitations of the compressor and the pressure losses in the oil separator. Similar to the condenser, the evaporator is significantly oversized for the observed operating points, leading to a very small temperature approach at the hot end of the evaporator. Together with the constant superheating of 20 K after the evaporator, this directly correlates the evaporating pressure to the heat source inlet temperature. As a consequence, the evaporating pressure increases from roughly 1.85 bar, over 3.37 bar to 5.8 bar for heat source temperatures of 55 °C, 75 °C and 95 °C, respectively. The respective suction gas density approximately doubles with each step in evaporation pressure, requiring significantly higher compressor speeds to convey the same mass flow at lower heat source temperatures. Accordingly, the upper speed limit is reached much faster for low heat source temperatures, severely limiting the operational range. Another detrimental effect reflected in Table A.1 is the disproportional large pressure losses over the oil separator for comparatively small mass flows with lower heat source temperatures. This can be attributed to the lower heat sink temperatures, which come along with the lower heat source temperatures. As described in Section 3.1.1, the small condenser pinch point directly correlates lower sink temperatures to lower condensation pressures, yielding a lower gas density after the compressor and, accordingly, higher volumetric flow rates and oil separator pressure losses.

As expected, an increased lift in the heat sink (and accordingly also the HTHP's temperature lift) results in a lower COP for a constant heat sink mass flow and heat source temperature. This effect is more pronounced for smaller heat source temperatures, where the disproportionate effect of oil separator pressure losses and the generally lower volumetric compressor efficiencies reduce the plant efficiency. For operating points with different heat source temperatures but the same heat sink conditions (i.e. \dot{m}_{CC} and ΔT_{44-43}), the COP is dominated by the volumetric and electrical efficiency. The same observations described in Section 3.1.1 can be made here.

Fig. A.3 shows the volumetric efficiency and the oil mass flow for the operating points presented in Table A.1. For all points, a relatively constant oil delivery between 20 and 30 g/s was chosen. For operating points with high compressor speeds (i.e. with a heat source temperature of 55 °C), this results in insufficient lubrication, yielding drastically reduced volumetric compressor efficiencies. This cannot be compensated by the beneficial effect of higher compressor speeds on the drive-train

Table A.1
Operational points of the HTHP derived from the application scenario.

T_{11} [°C]	T_{43} [°C]	\dot{m}_{ICC} [kg/s]	ΔT_{ICC} [°C]	\dot{m}_{wf} [kg/s]	n_{comp} [rpm]	Δp_{OS} [bar]	η_{vol} [%]	η_{mech} [%]	η_{el} [%]	COP	Limitation	Nr.
55	50	0.5	20	0.156	2476	0.79	60.4	49.1	93.0	4.96	–	1
		0.5	30	0.140	3900	1.08	35.3	31.8	96.0	3.54	–	2
		1.0	20 (17)	0.113	4000	1.55	27.7	23.3	95.9	4.52	n_{comp}	3
		1.0	30	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	n_{comp}	4
		1.5	20	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	n_{comp}	5
		1.5	30	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	n_{comp}	6
75	70	0.5	20	0.173	1624	0.57	57.4	44.8	91.9	5.17	–	7
		0.5	30	0.236	2558	0.93	50.3	46.8	94.9	4.27	–	8
		1.0	20	0.298	3147	1.57	52.3	44.7	95.6	4.89	–	9
		1.0	30	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	$n_{\text{comp}}, \Delta p_{\text{OS}}$	10
		1.5	20	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	$n_{\text{comp}}, \Delta p_{\text{OS}}$	11
		1.5	30	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	$n_{\text{comp}}, \Delta p_{\text{OS}}$	12
95	90	0.5	20	0.203	1216	0.44	52.6	63.1	90.6	4.75	–	13
		0.5	30	0.315	1807	0.78	55.1	46.0	93.4	4.19	–	14
		1.0	20	0.393	2127	1.25	58.8	37.4	94.2	5.26	–	15
		1.0	30 (25)	0.649	2847	1.84	76.4	56.8	95.5	4.60	V-38, Δp_{OS}	16
		1.5	20 (17)	0.564	3099	1.94	69.9	44.0	95.7	4.76	V-38, Δp_{OS}	17
		1.5	30	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	V-38, Δp_{OS}	18

Fig. A.3. Volumetric efficiency as well as oil flow over compressor speed of the HTHP for application-based evaluation.

efficiency (depicted in Fig. A.4(a)), yielding lower COPs compared to comparable heat sink conditions at higher heat source temperatures.

Considering the relative proximity of many data points and the indicated error margins of the volumetric efficiency in Fig. A.3, trends that do not strictly follow the behaviour described in Section 3.1.1 do not disprove the general behaviour described there. Especially higher volumetric efficiencies at high working fluid mass flows are most likely wrongfully increased by the presence of oil in the mass flow measurement FR21 as explained in Appendix A.1.4.

The generally high electrical drive-train efficiencies observed in Fig. 5(b) are confirmed by the values presented in Fig. A.4(a). The high efficiencies observed over a large speed range enable a good COP for most operating points despite relatively low volumetric and mechanical compressor efficiencies, further validating the design choice of using a reluctance motor for enhanced part load efficiency. The shift of point 1 in Fig. A.4(a) can be attributed to a comparatively low motor torque for this point, slightly lowering the electrical efficiency. Similar to Figs. 8, A.4(b) confirms that the mechanical compressor efficiency is dominated by the volumetric efficiency and does not reflect the detrimental effects of over- and under-compression. Also, the relatively

large error margin of the mechanical efficiency indicates a limited suitability of this parameter for explaining the plant behaviour.

A.3. Supplementary material ORC: Mechanical expander efficiency, filling factor and oil-separator

While the mechanical efficiency's general curvature from Fig. 13(a) can be explained by the pressure ratio, the relative trends of the individual curves need further explanation. For the lowest pump speed, the mechanical efficiency is lower for a heat source temperature of 110 °C at higher pressure ratios and then increasingly matches the efficiency at a heat source temperature of 130 °C for lower pressure ratios. For the higher two pump speeds, the mechanical efficiency is initially also lower at lower heat source temperatures and higher pressure ratios. However, this changes when the pressure ratio falls below a value of roughly 3.1–3.2. This behaviour can be explained by the filling factor of the expander. For all curves, a lower pressure ratio generally means higher expander speed. As depicted in Fig. 13(b), the expander's filling factor drastically decreases from high initial values with rising expander speed and approaches a value of 1 at high speeds. This is consistent with the expected behaviour described in literature [37]. The higher conveyed volumetric flow at higher expander speeds reduces the impact of internal leakages and enhances the filling factor. The minor vertical scatter of the data points in Fig. 13(b) indicates a very low influence of the pressure differential on the filling factor. Consequently, only the machine speed needs to be considered when arguing with the filling factor in this case. The operating points with a heat source temperature of 130 °C exhibit consistently higher expander speeds at the same evaporation pressure and working fluid mass flow when compared to a heat source temperature of 110 °C. This is depicted for a heat source mass flow of 1.0 kg/s and different pump speeds in Fig. A.5(a). As previously described, the working fluid's evaporator outlet temperature mostly matches the heat source inlet temperature (c.f. Fig. 11(b)), resulting in lower gas densities at comparable evaporation pressures and higher heat source temperatures. At a constant mass flow rate (induced by the constant working fluid pump speed) this results in higher expander speeds. The significantly lower expander speeds for a working fluid pump speed of 25% (as seen in Fig. A.5(a)) yield comparatively high filling factors and explain the generally lower mechanical efficiencies for this pump speed in Fig. 13(a).

Fig. A.4. Electrical drive-train efficiency (a) and mechanical compressor efficiency (b) of the HTHP for application-based evaluation.

Fig. A.5. Expander speed (a) and oil separator pressure loss (b) with $\dot{m}_{HC} = 1.0$ kg/s for ORC operation.

The sharp increase of the filling factor at low expander speeds leads to a disproportional increase of the filling factor when the expander speed is slightly reduced in the lower speed range. This especially affects the operating points at a heat source temperature of 110 °C as indicated in Fig. 13(b) for low speeds. That explains the high difference in mechanical efficiency for different heat source temperatures at a pump speed of 25% (resulting in generally lower expander speeds) and higher pressure ratios in Fig. 13(a). The increasing expander speed at lower pressure ratios causes the filling factor to increase and since the differences in the filling factor get less pronounced between the two heat source temperatures, the mechanical efficiency approaches too. At larger expander speeds, which is the case for pump speeds of 35% and especially 45%, the difference in filling factor for the different heat source temperatures increasingly reduces with increasing expander speed until it practically disappears. Hence, the difference in mechanical efficiency caused by the filling factor disappears at relatively higher pressure ratios compared to the pump speed of 25% in Fig. 13(a).

The reason why the mechanical efficiency at 110 °C heat source temperature exceeds the values for the higher temperature for the upper two working fluid pump speeds has two potential explanations. One is rooted in the friction losses, which increase with rising expander speed. The generally higher expander speeds at 130 °C (c.f. Fig. A.5(a)) could lead to higher friction losses at lower pressure ratios, disproportionately reducing the mechanical efficiency for the higher heat source temperature in the higher speed range. However, the difference in mechanical efficiency is too large at low pressure ratios to be explained by friction losses alone. The second effect increasing the mechanical efficiency are heat losses at the expander, which reduce the

outlet enthalpy and consequently (wrongfully) increase the mechanical efficiency according to Eq. (6). Due to the direct coupling of expander and generator, the air flow from the generator cooling is directed towards the expander and, unfortunately, also results in active cooling of the expander. This effect increases with rising expander speeds and is most likely significant despite the expander's thermal insulation.

Finally, the pressure loss in the oil separator needs to be considered. Fig. A.5(b) shows the pressure losses in the oil separator for a heat source mass flow of 1.0 kg/s. As expected, higher flow rates (correlated to higher working fluid pump speeds) lead to a significant increase in pressure losses. While this reduces the overall cycle efficiency of the ORC at higher mass flow rates, the detrimental effect seems to be compensated by the previously described benefits of higher expander speed on filling factor and mechanical expander efficiency. The pressure losses for a heat source temperature of 130 °C are consistently higher. This can be attributed to the lower gas density at the evaporator outlet and, accordingly, higher volumetric flow rates entering the oil separator at comparable mass flow rates. Despite the higher oil separator pressure losses, the cycle efficiency is still better for higher heat source temperatures at otherwise unchanged cycle parameters, indicating that the Carnot efficiency has an overall larger impact on the cycle efficiency than the pressure losses in the oil separator. Nonetheless, a larger oil separator would benefit the cycle efficiency by reducing the pump work, which is dissipated as oil separator pressure loss. More importantly, the separation efficiency in the oil separator severely limited the oil dosage during ORC operation. Highly insufficient oil separation was observed for larger working fluid mass flows, which was reflected by large liquid fractions in the sight glass at the oil separator gas outlet line, as well as the high pressure losses. Consequently, only

Fig. A.6. Gross electric generator power (including inverter losses) at a pump speed of 25% (a) and 35% (b) for ORC operation.

Fig. A.7. Gross electric generator power (including inverter losses) at a pump speed of 45% (a) and drive-train, i.e. generator and inverter, efficiency map (b) for ORC operation.

a fraction of the cycled oil was yielded in the oil separator's collection vessel and the oil mass flow towards the expander was mostly restricted to values below 10 g/s to prevent dry-running of the collector. The large amount of oil leaving the separator with the outlet gas seemingly ensures proper lubrication and sealing of the rotor profiles, as the filling factors are mostly within a reasonable range (c.f. Fig. 13(b)). However, low oil dosage towards the expander via the oil system can damage the internal sealings and bearings in the long run and should consequently be avoided. The only way to improve this is with a larger and more efficient oil separator.

A.4. Supplementary material ORC: Generator power output and drive-train losses

See Figs. A.6 and A.7.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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